

Canada Research Chair in
Media, Disabilities and (Self) Representations

**Questionnaire
Production member**

Linked to the Disability and Deafhood Database
chairemediashandicaps.uqam.ca/database/

PURPOSE OF THE CRCMHA

IDENTIFY groups living with one or more disabilities that are predominantly represented in the Canadian media (1980-2020) as well as the characteristics of these (self)representations, the characters represented and their authors;

To better UNDERSTAND the relation between contemporary media representations of disability (2000-2020) and their uses by people with disabilities;

Determine measures likely to IMPROVE over time the presence and inclusion of people with disabilities in media content through the development and implementation of inclusive "media policies" promoting the full social participation of the groups concerned.

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UQÀM | **Chaire de recherche du Canada
sur les médias, les handicaps
et les (auto)représentations**
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CRCMHA - Questionnaire - Production member

1) Name
Open data

Role(s)

2) Created by
Check box

3) Illustration / Drawing
Check box

4) Directed by
Check box

5) Script by
Check box

Type of disability (production member) (Statistics Canada)

6) Sensory disability
Check box

7) Physical disability
Check box

8) Pain-related disability
Check box

9) Mental health-related disability
Check box

10) Cognitive disability
Check box

11) Unknown disability
Check box

12) Production member is neurodivergent
Check box

12B) Production member is Deaf
Check box

13) Media production includes a character with a disability who is (or is based on) a loved one/family member of the production creators
Check box

14) Notes on production member
Open data

15) Problems with production member
Open data